

Security audit of Internet of Things home automation system

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Abstract

The Internet of Things (IoT) is currently one of the key technologies that brings smart services into many areas of everyday life. Among others, IoT can be deployed in home automation systems, making it possible to turn normal houses into smart homes. Smart home technologies can help with simple tasks like adjusting the comfort conditions and controlling lighting. They can also help with daily routines by providing calendar information, a schedule for events and a weather forecast. Because elements of IoT systems are expected to be connected to the network, one important challenge with smart home systems is to maintain the security and privacy of users' data. This paper presents the security audit of a popular home automation Domoticz, which shows that developers are aware of the issue and try to keep a satisfactory level of software they offer. Based on the results of the security audit some recommendations were specified which could help to further enhance protection against cyber threats for future versions of the Domoticz system.

Keywords: Internet of Things; Cybersecurity; Security audit; Home automation; Domoticz

1. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a fast-developing technology that enables the connection of devices and objects themselves, and the connection of these devices to the data processing servers. IoT technology is used in many areas of life, including healthcare, communication and transport, power and goods delivery, buildings and cities management [42], environmental monitoring, agriculture [35] and many others. An example, which is becoming popular, is the use of this technology in homes, creating a so-called smart home [36]. Devices installed in buildings can help manage the whole house from a single point or even from outside with the use of an internet connection. IoT makes it possible to control heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) [44], light intensity, home appliances like vacuum cleaners, microwave ovens, dishwashers, washing machines and many others. Advanced control algorithms connected with green power sources can help to optimise energy consumption [18] and reduce the cost of energy by dynamically adjusting the momentary energy use to the current price or generation level by a photovoltaic system [43]. This increases the use of green energy instead of traditional fossil-generated. IoT also helps users to have better comfort. From one place, using, for example, a phone or tablet, one can check what is currently connected and use electricity and control light scenes or household appliances like Smart TVs, audio systems and cleaning robots. In addition to home devices, outdoor devices can also be connected to the system. This includes surveillance cameras, motion sensors, automatic gates, and increasingly popular autonomous lawnmower robots. By connecting to one system, homeowners can manage their homes, even if they are in a distant location.

Devices operating in the Internet of Things systems are computers, often connected to networks and visible on the Internet. It exposes them to the same risk of cyberattack as other computers on the network. It is essential for the users that the systems they use are safe and protected from possible attacks. This paper presents the security evaluation of a popular IoT smart home system, Domoticz, showing its vulnerabilities and proposing measures for threat avoidance.

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2. Related works

IoT devices and infrastructure can be vulnerable to a variety of attacks, including Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) [3], Man in the Middle (MitM) [6][12], Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) [2], SQL injection [32][23] and others. There exist known successful attacks on IoT devices, as confirmed in the literature. One of the most widely recognised is the DDoS attack [4][3] by the Mirai botnet [21]. The privacy and security of smart home systems are important barriers to the installation of such a system for potential users. Consumers considering smart home deployment are worried that potential attacks could lead to a loss of control of smart homes [11]. That's why the research on the protection of smart home systems, IoT devices, and infrastructure is currently the topic of high importance.

IoT systems are usually considered in terms of several basic layers. Literature knows the three or five-layered approaches as described in [33]. There is also a four-layer model which includes: Sensing (perception) Layer, Network Layer, Data Processing Layer, and Application Layer [41]. Despite the model, devices at any layer can be targeted by an attack. The paper [24] focuses on the security challenges in IoT-based smart homes. It presents the different layers of IoT technologies, such as sensors, networks, computing, and applications, as well as the potential threats that may occur at each of these layers. The paper also discusses possible solutions that can help secure smart homes against cyberattacks. This is important for systems such as Domoticz that manage multiple IoT devices.

The speed of development of the Internet of Things device market means that manufacturers often have a problem with applying appropriate security measures to systems and devices. In each area of IoT deployment, devices may require a different type of security. An additional problem is the fact that these devices are small in size and constrained in computational capacity, and therefore often have too little computing power to implement advanced, sophisticated security algorithms. Sometimes the devices use widely-known simple passwords for the authentication [30], which makes them extremely prone to the attack, compromising the whole network. Attacks in the perception layer are analysed in [19]. Detection of attacks and intrusion can use the deep learning methods as described in [8].

Currently, the most popular method of forming IoT networks is to use wireless data communication. Network layer security is broadly analysed in papers considering sensor networks [28][37][26]. The dynamic development of the Internet of Things makes it vulnerable to various types of attacks. Due to the extensive utilisation of the machine-to-machine (M2M) communication model, which needs to operate without user intervention, the biggest challenge can be found in the device authorisation and authentication procedure [1].

Security of the data processing layer is discussed in [38]. Attacks can be targeted at both clients and servers as described in [40]. The papers [43] and [20] consider, among others, security aspects of data management in IoT systems. The authors of [20] made a detailed review of a variety of possible authentication protocols for IoT, and the authors of [43] write about blockchain use to enhance the cybersecurity of smart home systems.

Domoticz is one of the most popular home automation systems. Authors of [34] assessed 20 open-source home automation systems and found Domoticz the second one according to the criteria they defined. One of the methods of interfacing the home automation system is the use of a voice-controlled device - a smart speaker. The authors of [22] made a review on the level of trust of users in voice-controlled home automation systems. To mitigate the risks and reduce the possibility of a successful cyberattack, some standards were defined [39]. An important method of assessing if the system is protected against threats is a security audit. In this paper, we present the results of a security audit of the Domoticz system performed in 2017 [5], 2018 [7], and 2024 [25], highlighting the evolution of its security features.

3. Research methodology and tools

The aim of the work was to perform a security audit of the Domoticz system and compare the test results with the results obtained in 2017 and 2018. The Raspberry Pi 4 was selected as the test stand, on which the Domoticz system was installed. To perform the security audit, a Kali Linux virtual machine was used with the set of required tools installed.

3.1. Security audit

A security audit is the process of assessing the IT security of a system. Its purpose is to find any potential security gaps and vulnerabilities in IT systems. By conducting security audits, companies can proactively implement

mechanisms to increase system security and protect sensitive information. It should be conducted at least once a year to ensure that security is up to date. A security audit usually consists of several stages:

- Preparation and planning – defining what is to be the subject of the audit and its scope.
- Gathering information – at this point, it is important to review and analyse the documentation. If the audit is carried out on behalf of the company, you can try to collect information from employees or contractors.
- Analysis and risk assessment – potential threats should be identified, for example, finding security gaps or configuration errors.
- Security testing – conducting penetration tests and analysing vulnerabilities to attacks.
- Reporting – preparing a report and proposing possible recommendations to improve the quality of security.

3.2. *Domoticz*

There are many home automation systems available on the market. Some of them are commercial, and others are offered as open-source software. The system chosen to conduct the research for this work is called Domoticz. Domoticz is an open-source home automation system which allows the user to monitor and control various IoT devices. It is one of the most universal systems. It is available for Windows, Linux, macOS and Raspberry Pi platforms. This system is free and easy to install and use, which makes it very popular. The latest available, at the time of making the research, version of the Domoticz system, 2024.7, was installed for the purpose of conducting the study. This version was released in July 2024, which indicates that the creators are constantly updating the system.

3.3. *Hardware used*

For the purpose of the research, two hardware platforms were used. Raspberry Pi 4 for Domoticz installation and a PC for the Kali Linux auditing software.

Raspberry Pi 4 is a single-board microcomputer. The version used in the tests has 4GB of RAM, four USB ports and a USB-C power supply connector. This board can communicate with other devices using Wi-Fi and Bluetooth. Raspberry Pi runs a dedicated operating system called Raspbian Pi OS. This is a Debian-based distribution tailored to this microcomputer.

For the auditing software package, a normal PC was used with a virtual machine environment. No special requirements are specified for this system, as Kali Linux is not demanding in terms of hardware performance.

3.4. *Kali Linux*

The research stand was a PC machine running the Kali Linux system [13]. This is a Debian-based operating system designed for cybersecurity engineers. It offers many built-in tools for various security-related tasks. The main applications of the Kali Linux system include penetration testing [31]. To fully utilise its capabilities and conduct a security audit, it was necessary to install additional software, including Nmap, Nikto, OWASP ZAP and WhatWeb.

Nmap is one of the most popular tools used for scanning and mapping networks [15]. It connects to individual ports on the system to see which ones are open. Any open port not assigned to any service can be a potential "doorway" for an attacker.

Nikto is a scanner [14] that performs fast HTTP queries on servers, looking for configuration errors, outdated software, malicious files and resources. It can also detect XSS [10] and SQL Injection [32] vulnerabilities.

WhatWeb performs a quick scan of multiple pages to find their configuration. The tool [17] sends simple HTTP requests to the page and analyses its headers. It also examines the page content looking for characteristic code fragments or configuration files, to find the side-channel attack possibility [29].

OWASP ZAP (Zed Attack Proxy) [16] identifies threats for known vulnerabilities such as SQL Injection [23] or XSS [2]. It performs automatic application scanning, fuzzing - injecting random data to see how the application reacts to it [9], and spidering - automatic mapping of all entry points to the application [27].

Figure 1: Coloured flags returned by OWASP ZAP tool.

```
Nmap scan report for 192.168.0.175
Host is up (0.023s latency).
Not shown: 65532 filtered tcp ports (no-response)
PORT      STATE SERVICE      VERSION
443/tcp   open  ssl/https
6144/tcp  open  statscil-lm?
8080/tcp  open  http-proxy
```

Figure 2: Results of the Nmap tool.

3.5. OWASP ZAP

The OWASP ZAP application returns information on the severity of the detected vulnerability. They are marked with four coloured flags as shown in Fig. 1.

The red flag indicates a high level of threat. These are serious security threats. They should be analysed and fixed as a priority. They pose a high risk to both applications and user data that may be leaked. If the company does not prevent these threats as a priority, it will allow an attacker to enter the entire system and obtain sensitive data.

The orange flag alerts are not as important as the alerts marked in red. They indicate potential problems and vulnerabilities in security that could be exploited by hackers. However, for this to happen, additional factors would usually have to be met. Thanks to this, these alerts are not as high a priority as red alerts.

The yellow flag indicates alerts that are worth analysing and making corrections to the system. Most often, these are minor problems that will not allow an attacker to easily get into the system.

The blue flag alerts are informational ones that act as a hint or reflection. They can be ignored because they do not require immediate intervention, but they are worth monitoring.

4. Security audit of Domoticz home automation system

Following the security audit procedure, first of all, there is a need to collect information about the system that is the subject of the tests. For this purpose, the Domoticz documentation was read to obtain as much information about the system as possible. It contains guides for using the system, tips for the installation process, and many other guides that were added there by the creators of the system. While performing this research, the documentation content update date was April 2024, which may indicate that the Domoticz system was constantly being developed and updated. No information was found there that would indicate significant security holes.

4.1. Port and server configuration scanning

Having information about the investigated system, a search for potential security vulnerabilities was performed. First, port scanning was performed. The Nmap tool was used for this. It was started manually and automatically scanned all ports for open ones. The scan results are shown in Fig. 2.

The Nmap tool found three open ports. Port 443 is used for HTTPS, and port 8080 for HTTP. The last port, 6144, is used for establishing the hierarchical connection between many cooperating instances of Domoticz, where one of them plays the role of primary and the others are secondary systems.

The second scan was made with the Nikto tool. It was started manually to search for known vulnerabilities. The results are presented in Fig. 3. It can be seen that 6 potential security vulnerabilities were detected on the server.

Nikto has received information that the "Access-Control-Allow-Origin" header is configured as "*", which is too broad. When processing sensitive data, this system is vulnerable to CORS (Cross-Origin Resource Sharing) attacks.

The Nikto scanner also received information that the server does not set the "X-Frame-Options" header. This may expose the system to clickjacking attacks.

The server also does not set the "X-Content-Type-Options" header. The lack of this header may expose the system to MIME-type recognition deficiencies.

```
+ Server: No banner retrieved
+ /: Retrieved access-control-allow-origin header: *.
+ /: The anti-clickjacking X-Frame-Options header is not present. See: https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/HTTP/Headers/X-Frame-Options
+ /: The X-Content-Type-Options header is not set. This could allow the user agent to render the content of the site in a different fashion to the MIME type. See: https://www.netsparker.com/web-vulnerability-scanner/vulnerabilities/missing-content-type-header/
+ /: Uncommon header 'x-content-encoding-over-network' found, with contents: gzip.
+ /: Web Server returns a valid response with junk HTTP methods which may cause false positives.
+ /.well-known/openid-configuration: OpenID Provider Configuration Information.
+ 26661 requests: 0 error(s) and 6 item(s) reported on remote host
+ End Time: 2024-08-30 23:03:52 (GMT-4) (333 seconds)
+ 1 host(s) tested
```

Figure 3: Results of the Nikto tool.

The next piece of information obtained by the Nikto tool is the use of the "x-content-encoding-over-network" header with the gzip value. This is an unusual solution aimed at increasing data compression.

Nikto also provides information that the server responds to requests with unusual HTTP methods, which can lead to false-positive security checks. This is not in line with standard actions in such cases. Usually, servers reject such requests.

The last issue detected by the Nikto tool is the availability of the OpenID Provider configuration on the server. This is indicated by the endpoint: ".well-known/openid-configuration". Authentication mechanisms based on the OpenID Connect protocol are supported. Access to this endpoint does not provide sensitive data, but it can provide information about the implementation, and therefore, it can help attackers carry out an attack.

The next step of a security audit was to perform a scan using the WhatWeb tool. Started manually, performed scanning for known vulnerabilities. The results are presented in Fig. 4. Scanning with the WhatWeb tool provided some information.

In the scan results, there is information that the site uses Bootstrap. This is a popular framework that is used to create websites. The scanner detected that the framework version used by the site is 3.4.0. This version is no longer supported. Using a non-latest version of Bootstrap or any other framework may introduce security holes as newer versions are released with patches to improve security.

Another, less important piece of information is "Country[RESERVED][ZZ]". It says that the geographical location of the system is not known. It does not affect various types of vulnerabilities and threats in any way.

The next information is the use of the HTML5 standard. This is the latest version of the HTML language used to create websites.

jQuery [3.6.0] is a JavaScript library. It is used especially for manipulating the Document Object Model (DOM). It was designed to simplify coding in this language. Version 3.6.0 of the library used by the manufacturers is a stable version of the library, which is still used on many websites and is relatively up-to-date. The latest version is 3.7.1.

The Matomo element means that the site contains software used to analyse traffic on the site. However, information about the version of this software is probably behind a firewall, because there is no information about what version the site is currently using.

Script[text/ng-template] means that the site uses AngularJS templates. Information about the exact version of the AngularJS library is behind a firewall, and tools used to check it do not provide any search results. Manually checking the source files of the site gives the result that there is no file with data about AngularJS.

Another component of the WhatWeb tool results is "Title[Domoticz]". This is information about the title of the HTML page. It does not indicate any threats to which the system could be exposed.

UncommonHeaders[access-control-allow-origin] is the CORS header "Access-Control-Allow-Origin". It is used to control which sources can access resources on the server. When properly configured, it does not pose a threat to the system.

The last part of the response from WhatWeb is "X-UA-Compatible[IE=edge]:". This specifies whether the page should be rendered in the latest version of Internet Explorer.

```
http://192.168.0.175:8080 [200 OK] Bootstrap[2.3.0,3.4.0], Country[RESERVED][
ZZ], HTML5, IP[192.168.0.175], JQuery[3.6.0], Matomo, Script[text/ng-template
], Title[Domoticz], UncommonHeaders[access-control-allow-origin], X-UA-Compat
ible[IE=edge]
```

Figure 4: Results of the WhatWeb tool.

- > Absence of Anti-CSRF Tokens (4)
- > Content Security Policy (CSP) Header Not Set (11)
- > Cross-Domain Misconfiguration (165)
- > Missing Anti-clickjacking Header (5)
- > Vulnerable JS Library (7)
- > Timestamp Disclosure - Unix (7)
- > X-Content-Type-Options Header Missing (165)
- > Content-Type Header Missing
- > Information Disclosure - Suspicious Comments (98)

Figure 5: Results of the OWASP ZAP tool.

4.2. Penetration tests

The advanced penetration tests were done with the use of the OWASP ZAP tool. The test was performed as an automatic test of the attack type. The results of the test are presented in Fig. 5. The tool detected 9 different alerts.

Red flag vulnerabilities. It is important to note that the OWASP ZAP tool did not detect any alerts requiring immediate intervention, i.e. those belonging to the group of alerts marked with a red flag.

Orange flag vulnerabilities. The tool detected five medium-severity vulnerabilities.

The first detected alert from the medium "orange" category is "Absence of Anti-CSRF Tokens". This poses a security risk to the system. CSRF attacks rely on the exploitation of the trust of a website user. The attacker forces the victim to perform certain actions without their knowledge, for example, changing account settings. This may result in the disclosure of confidential information, thanks to excessive account permissions.

The next "orange" alert is related to the Content Security Policy (CSP). It is a mechanism by which resources are controlled that are loaded and executed by the browser. The main goal of CSP is to prevent XSS attacks and data injection attacks. These attacks can lead to the disclosure of confidential data or the destruction of a website. Content Security Policy sets appropriate HTTP headers to distinguish allowed content sources.

The Cross-Domain Misconfiguration alert refers to a misconfiguration of Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS) on a web server. This can be used by an attacker to gain access to data. This configuration allows access to external domains and to some APIs without authentication. This is a serious problem because an attacker can find information that should be protected, such as an IP whitelist. This list is a collection of addresses that have more privileges than other users.

The "Missing Anti-clickjacking Header" alert refers directly to the missing X-Frame-Options header. This exposes the site to ClickJacking attacks. The attacker can trick the victim into clicking buttons or performing some action without their knowledge.

The last vulnerability classified by the OWASP ZAP tool as medium risk is the vulnerable JS Library. The scanner has detected that the site still uses the outdated jQuery UI library. Using non-latest versions of libraries may expose the system/site to threats related to exploiting their vulnerabilities. This allows hackers to easily get into the system.

Yellow flag vulnerabilities. The OWASP ZAP detected two low-severity vulnerabilities.

The first vulnerability discovered by the OWASP ZAP tool is the timestamp disclosure. These can be used by attackers to detect application activity and help them synchronise their attack on the system.

Another vulnerability concerns the lack of setting the X-Content-Type-Options header to nosniff. If it is not set, browsers may incorrectly determine the content type of the response as different from what it actually is. Such actions are called MIME-sniffing. Such an attack can occur when using older versions of Internet Explorer, Google Chrome, Safari, and Opera browsers. Thanks to this method, attackers can easily intentionally interfere with the content of the page in such a way as to lead to a data leak. It may also be easier to perform an XSS attack. A potential danger can be considered as a JavaScript script.

Blue flag vulnerabilities. The last group of detected alerts are informational. There are two such alerts.

The first one concerns detected suspicious comments in the server response. In the cases studied, no sensitive information was found that could lead to the leakage of information about the application structure or potential security holes, so it was assigned to the category of informational alerts.

The second alert, also detected by the Nmap tool, is the open port 6144. It is related to the ability to share devices and connect several cooperating Domoticz systems remotely.

5. Results

The comparison of the results of open ports detection from 2017, 2018 and 2024 is presented in Table 1. As can be seen, they are similar to each other, although in 2018, the developers of the Domoticz system closed the previously open port 22, which posed a threat to the security of the entire system.

Ports open in 2017	Ports open in 2018	Ports open in 2024
8080	8080	8080
6144	6144	6144
443	443	443
22	-	-

The summary of results obtained in 2024 compared to the results from 2017 and 2018 is presented in Table 2. In 2024, no problems were detected related to sharing data in the URL or those related to faulty access control. This may indicate that the creators of the system have placed a strong emphasis on improving security.

6. Recommendations

Based on the results of the tests, it is possible to define recommendations to improve the security of the Domoticz system by fixing the most important issues identified. As there are no critical alerts detected, the recommendations don't need to be implemented immediately, but they should be considered for introduction in the following versions of the system.

Outdated jQuery UI and Bootstrap libraries. It is recommended to update libraries to the latest version because some vulnerabilities were identified in previous versions. For example, older versions of the Bootstrap library increase the possibility of a successful XSS attack.

CORS configuration. It is recommended to configure the CORS header to limit access to trusted domains only. Another solution is to remove these headers completely.

Absence of anti-CSRF token. It is recommended to use libraries and frameworks that already have built-in protection mechanisms against CSRF attacks. When submitting forms, they should add a unique CSRF token that can minimise the occurrence of this type of attack. An additional protection against these attacks is the introduction of two-step verification.

Absence of X-Frame-Options header. It is recommended to set the X-Frame-Options header or set the "frame-ancestors" directive in Content-Security-Policy. The second option is a newer and more precise solution. It allows specifying specific domains that can set the page in a frame.

General recommendations. The system should use the newest stable versions of libraries and frameworks, avoid sending unnecessary information like timestamps and comments, and close unnecessary ports.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

Summarising the conducted research, it can be stated that the Domoticz system is still being developed. The developers not only improve and extend their functionality but also take care of security by fixing critical errors detected during previous research. A login screen for the administrator has been added, and after several unsuccessful attempts to enter data, the page redirects to the "end of the internet", a subpage created specifically for this purpose. This means that a person who does not know the password to the account will not enter the system. Another fixed vulnerability is account permissions. Previously, the user account could change into an administrator account on its

own. Currently, it is not possible to perform such an action. The creators of the system also took care of the security of the system by hiding certain information from users and outsiders. During the research in 2024, it was not possible to obtain information about the version of most of the libraries used on the website. This may indicate that this information was hidden behind a firewall. No data sharing in the URL was also detected. Previously, sensitive data was shared there, which was very dangerous for the system. The update of the libraries used on the site was also taken into account. They have been updated since the previous study performed in 2018, but the latest versions that would maximise security in the system are still not being used. The research performed proves that all critical vulnerabilities were fixed, and so, the Domoticz home automation system offers not only an interesting and exhaustive set of features but also a satisfactory level of security. As new possible attack methods emerge daily, we plan to conduct similar research every few years to monitor the security of the Domoticz system continuously.

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Severity level	2017		Table 2: Detected vulnerabilities 2018		2024	
	Vulnerability	CVSS v3 grade	Vulnerability	CVSS v3 grade	Vulnerability	CVSS v3 grade
Red	XSS	8.1	Access control	8.5		
Red	Sensitive data in URL	8.0	Sensitive data in URL	8.3	-	-
Red	-	-	Improper queries	8.3	-	-
Orange	Outdated JQuery-ui	5.9	Outdated i18next	6.1	Outdated JQuery-ui	6.0
Orange	Outdated Bootstrap	5.9	Outdated Bootstrap	6.1	Outdated Bootstrap	6.0
Orange	-	-	Cross-site scripting	6.8	Improper CORS configuration	6.5
Orange	-	-	-	-	Absence of anti-CSRF tokens	6.5
Orange	-	-	-	-	Absence of X-Frame-control header	6.5
Yellow	Absence of security headers	3.4	Absence of security headers	3.7	Absence of security headers	4.3
Yellow	-	-	-	-	Timestamp disclosure	3.7
Blue	Open port 6144	0.0	Open port 6144	0.0	Open port 6144	0.0
Blue	Open port 22	0.0	Outdated AngularJS	0.0	Unneeded comments in the response	0.0
Blue	-	-	Outdated angular-md5	0.0	-	-
Blue	-	-	Outdated angular UI bootstrap	0.0	-	-
Blue	-	-	Outdated WOW	0.0	-	-
Blue	-	-	Outdated Ion Sound	0.0	-	-